

SELF-CONSISTENT MODELLING OF DAMAGED ELASTIC BEHAVIOUR USING RELIABILITY APPROACH

F. Desrumaux, F. Meraghni, and M.L. Benzeggagh

*Université de Technologie de Compiègne, LG2mS, Polymères et Composites
CNRS-UPRESA 6066, B.P. 20529
60205 Compiègne Cedex, France*

SUMMARY: The general purpose of this work is to study the damaged elastic behaviour for an aligned and a random discontinuous fibre composite. In this work, the self-consistent model of Mori and Tanaka is coupled with statistical strength theories to predict the mechanical behaviour of composite materials. The Micro/Macro model used here can estimate the state of stress into the fibre, the matrix and on the basis of the Mura's works, the stress states at the interface. Each failure of fibre, matrix and interface is simulated as stochastic phenomenon and governed by a probabilistic law. In fact, microcracks density inside the matrix or the fibres governs the damage accumulation. These densities increase according to probabilistic functions, which are obtained from the Weibull law. The reliability approach can describe the progressive damage accumulation. Hence, the prediction of composite materials failure based on a probabilistic approach seems more accurate and realistic than a deterministic approach based on maximum or quadratic stress criteria.

KEYWORDS: Self-consistent model, Reliability approach, Weibull law, Mechanical behaviour

INTRODUCTION

The aim of this paper is to describe the behaviour of fibre reinforced composites using statistical tools and probabilistic approaches, which govern the strength of composites material. In fact, damage can be initiated and growth inside each phase constituting the composite material. These phases are the inclusions (fibres), the matrix and the interface between the fibre and the matrix. The micromechanical model of Mori and Tanaka [1-8-9-10-11-12-13-14] can estimate the state of stress inside the matrix and the fibre when a macroscopic stress is applied. In addition, using the works of Mura and Chang [11], it is possible to calculate the state of stress at the interface. The interfacial decohesion and the matrix degradation has been modelled by Meraghni [8-9]. In this work, the damage accumulation is obtained by a progressive introduction of microcracks at the constituents scale. The evolution of microcracks density is probabilistic in nature and can be the onset of

the damage of each phase under a macroscopic stress. In the first time, this macroscopic solicitation is only of tension. Except for the case of the interface, the failure of each phase occurs for this same solicitation (tension). A combination between the normal and the shear stress induces the interfacial decohesion.

The probabilistic failure of the interface associated with the self-consistent model applied according to the Mori-Tanaka scheme has been previously treated by Fitoussi and al. [3]. the authors consider that the failure of the interface affect the elastic properties of the inclusion. The work presented here recalled this idea, except that the interfacial decohesion introduces voids or microcracks inside the matrix. Moreover, the damage accumulation process can occur inside matrix and fibre. To model the damage mechanisms of composite materials by a progressive introduction of voids or microcracks is a classical method in micromechanics [5]. These aspects of probabilistic strength have been previously developed by several authors. Goda [7] and Harlow [4] use these theories in a shear lag model (Cox's model) or a numerical model. In the present study, probabilistic considerations to model the damage process at the microscopic scale are coupled with a self-consistent model. Moreover, each phase is associated with a probabilistic failure criterion which dependent of the geometry of the phase considerate: Length for the fibre and volume for the matrix. However, to the interface case, there is not geometrical consideration.

MODEL COMPUTATION

The model of Mori and Tanaka can estimate the overall microscopic stress inside the fibre and the matrix when a macroscopic stress is applied Σ . In addition, the damaged rigidity tensor can be calculated. This tensor is function of S_i the Eschelby tensor, of C_i the rigidity tensor, of f_i the volume fraction of the inclusion (the subscript i designs the inclusion) as well as C_0 the rigidity tensor of the matrix and N the number of orientation family when the composite material is reinforced by random discontinuous fibre. In order to take into account the damage accumulation, a new class of inclusion (microcrack) must be introduce in the model. This class is pointed out by the subscript μ in the equations. Only the basic results from the Mori-Tanaka model are presented here but the reader is referred to the book by Mura [11]. Thus, the rigidity tensor of the damaged composite material can be expressed by [8-9]:

$$\tilde{C}_c = C_0 \left[I + \left(\sum_{i=1}^N f_i L_i + \sum_{\mu=1}^M f_{\mu} L_{\mu} \right) \left(I + \sum_{i=1}^N f_i (S_i - I) L_i + \sum_{\mu=1}^M f_{\mu} (S_{\mu} - I) L_{\mu} \right)^{-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

Where L_i is the localisation tensor:

$$L_i = -[(C_i - C_0)S_i + C_0]^{-1}(C_i - C_0) \quad (2)$$

To take into account the orientation of the fibre, it is necessary to introduce a rotation tensor T_i depending on θ_i (angle of rotation). This aspect is illustrated in fig. 1.

Figure 1: Composite containing randomly oriented ellipsoidal inclusions (bundles and microcracks). Local and global coordinate system relative to a bundle or microcrack.

The model used can estimate the state of stress inside the matrix σ_0 and the fibres σ_i when a macroscopic stress Σ is applied:

$$\sigma_0 = B_0 \Sigma$$

$$B_0 = C_0 \left[I + \sum_{i=1}^N f_i (S_i - I) L_i + \sum_{\mu=1}^M f_\mu (S_\mu - I) L_\mu \right]^{-1} C_0^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_i = B_i \Sigma$$

$$B_i = C_0 \left[(I + (S_i - I) L_i) \left(I + \sum_{i=1}^N f_i (S_i - I) L_i + \sum_{\mu=1}^M f_\mu (S_\mu - I) L_\mu \right) \right] C_0^{-1} \quad (4)$$

The works of Mura and Chang [12] is recalled to calculate the interfacial state of stress. For any point at the interface, the normal and the shear stress (σ_N , τ) can be expressed from the stress inside the fibre σ_i :

$$\sigma_N = \sigma_i \overline{nn} = \overline{Tn}$$

$$\tau = \sqrt{\|\overline{T}\|^2 - \sigma_N^2} \quad (5)$$

n is the normal vector describing the equator of the inclusion. The used failure criterion is a 'coulomb form'. It is a linear combination between the shear and the normal stress at the interface:

$$R_i = \sigma_N + \beta \tau \quad (6)$$

β and R_i are two parameters which characterise the interfacial decohesion. These parameters are experimentally identified using the pull out or push test for example [2].

The powerful of the developed model is that the damage process lead to the progressive degradation of each component. Moreover, this progressive damage is governed by

probabilistic considerations and not deterministic. The reliability of strength and the scale concepts are at the beginning of this point of view. These notions are developed in the book by Chou [13]. Furthermore, the relationship between strength variability and size effect has been studied by Winsnom [15], Hitchon [6], on composites materials. The strengths of each fibre are supposed to be independent and identically distributed random variables with common distribution function 'P_{fibre}(σ)', as follows:

$$P_{fibre}(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{L}{L_0}\left(\frac{\sigma}{X_{fibre}}\right)^{mf}\right] \quad (7)$$

Where X_{fibre} and mf are the Weibull moduli, L₀ is the original gage length, which has been used to determine the Weibull moduli, L and σ are the actual fibre length and stress respectively. The size effect is described by the length L. To assign strength for each fibre the reverse function of the equation 7 is written:

$$\sigma_{j-fibre}^{break} = X_{fibre} \left[\frac{L_0}{L} \ln\left(\frac{1}{1-z}\right) \right]^{1/mf} \quad (8)$$

z is a random number taken from the uniform distribution on the interval [0,1]. The same considerations have been used to characterise the damage evolution inside the matrix. Thus, the microcracks density is governed by a probabilistic function, which integrate a Weibull law:

$$P_{matrix}(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{V}{V_0}\left(\frac{\sigma}{X_{matrix}}\right)^{mm}\right] \quad (9)$$

X_{matrix} and mm are the both Weibull moduli. V₀ is the original gage volume, V and σ are the actual volume and stress. As the equation (7), the size effect is described by the term V. With the same considerations, the cumulative probability function at the interface can be expressed:

$$P_{interface}(R) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{R}{R_0}\right)^{mi}\right] \quad (10)$$

R₀ and mi are the both Weibull parameters. R is the actual Coulomb form defined by the equation 6. It should be noted that contrary to the other probability functions, the equation 10 doesn't depend on geometrical considerations (length or volume). In fact, these geometrical considerations are very difficult to apply at the interface. Thus, for this equation, the scaling concepts are not described. The damage accumulation in the matrix and at the interface is produced by the introduction of voids or microcracks of which the density is quantified through the probabilistic function (equation 9-10).

In the first time, the macroscopic solicitation is only a tension force. Under loading conditions, fibres are supposed broken only in tension. When this phenomenon occurs, the fibre inside its family is replaced by a void and the state of stress inside each component is recalculated with this new condition.

Figure 2: Flow chart

When the damage occurs inside the matrix, some microcracks are introduced in this one. The shape of this microcracks is cylindrical and its principle direction is transversal to the direction of the macroscopic force. The interfacial decohesion affects the matrix by the introduction of voids inside this one. The shape of these voids is also cylindrical and its principle direction is transversal to the direction of the fibres family, which is at the origin of the interfacial degradation. These assumptions are very strong but they allow simplifying the model. At the end of computation, the global failure of the composite material is defined when all the fibres or the matrix has broken.

Table 1: Parameters description

Parameter	Designation
C_0	Stiffness tensor of the matrix.
C_i	Stiffness tensor of the phase 'i'.
d_f	Fibre diameter.
L_f	Fibre length.
V_f	Fibre volume fraction.
N_{fam}	Number of orientation family.
V	Global volume.
$d\mu$	Microcrack diameter.
$L\mu$	Microcrack length.
X_{matrix}	Matrix tensile strength.
X_{fibre}	Fibre tensile strength.
σ_N	Maximum normal stress at the interface.
τ	Maximum shear stress at the interface.
β	Rate between the normal and shear stress at the interface.
mf	Fibre Weibull modulus.
L_0	Fibre gage length.
mi	Interface Weibull modulus.
mm	Matrix Weibull modulus.
V_0	Matrix gage volume.

The computation process is described by the flow chart (Fig. 2). Data input are introduced at the first step of the computation and are defined by the table 1. The self-consistent model associated with the probabilistic strength theory performs the 3-D behaviour of the composite material under a macroscopic tension stress.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Model validation

In this part, the developed model is validated on Randomly Oriented Discontinuous Fibre Composite (RODFC) in the case of a tension test. It is used to simulate the global behaviour of a (RODFC). The geometry and micromechanical parameters of the studied composite are depicted on the table 2 and 3, respectively. The probability functions that characterise the damage mechanism of each component are plotted in the figure 3. These curves are drawn using equations 7-9-10 and are characteristics of the degradation of each phase matrix, fibres and interface.

Table 2: Geometry parameters for the RODFC

Fibre diameter	$d = 14 \mu\text{m}$
Fibre volume fraction in the composite	$V_f = 0.50$

Figure 4 show the global result of this test. It is possible to see the simulated curve by the used model and the curves, which correspond to the experimental data. The used model over estimate the mechanical properties of the RODCF, whereas the mechanical behaviour is predicted with a good acurency.

Table 3: Mechanical parameters for the RODFC

Fibre	Young's modulus E_f	72000 MPa
	Poisson's rasion ν_f	0.25
	Tensile strength X_{fibre}	2400 MPa
	Weibull modulus m_f	3.5
	Gage length L_0	10 mm
Matrix	Young's modulus E_m	3000 MPa
	Poisson's rasion ν_m	0.4
	Tensile strength X_{matrix}	45
	Weibull modulus m_m	3.5
	Gage volume V_0	100
Interface	Maximum normal stress σ_N	45
	Maximum shear stress τ	25
	Weibull modulus	3.5
	Rate between the normal and shear stress β	0.1

As we can observe in table 4, the simulated results are in good agreement with the experimental database.

c)

Figure 3: Probability cumulative functions for a)the fibres b)the matrix c)the interface

Table 4: Comparison between model and experience for the RODFC

	E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	E_3 [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{13} [GPa]	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	X^+ [MPa]
Simulated	21	21	10.3	7.98	2.68	0.32	0.37	180
Experimental	20.3	20.3	12.4	7.07	3.9	0.33	0.38	152.8

Figure 4: Stress vs strain for a tension test on RODFC

Additional results

Figure 5 shows the evolution of microcrack densities on the whole composite for each component. For the studied material, the breakage is governed only by the matrix and interface degradation and the influence of the fibre breakage is low. The principle type of damaging is owing to the matrix breakage. In fact, the number of broken matrix elements

arises rapidly whereas the quantity of damaged interface arises slowly. This damage mechanism depicted in the figure 5 is characteristic of the investigated material (RODFC) and for an other one this mechanism will be different.

Figure 5: Damage evolution (microcracks density) for each component

CONCLUSION

The proposed model is validated on the RODFC and the results show a very great accuracy between calculated and experimental data. Moreover, different sort of damage mechanisms can be represented by the microcracks density functions. It is possible to know the principle phase (fibres, matrix or interface) which is responsible of the composite material breakage. The initiation and the evolution of the damage accumulation process can be viewed for each component. In fact, to model the behaviour of the composite material, the self-consistent model and the probabilistic approach taken together seem to be a more accurate method than the classical one. In addition, the results on the damage proposed by the model are very interesting despite the very strong assumptions introduce in the model. All the solicitations are in tension; the fibre and the matrix break under these ones. However, the model can introduce a damage, which is anisotropic. For each phase and for each orientation family, the microcrack have a specific orientation.

REFERENCES

1. Y. Benveniste, "A new approach to the application of Mori-Tanaka's theory", *Mechanics of materials*, Vol. 6, North-Holland, 1987, pp.147-157.
2. T.W. Clyne & P.J. Withers, "An introduction to metal matrix composites", *solid State Sciences series*, Cambridge University press, 1993.

3. J. Fitoussi, G. Guo & D. Baptiste, "A statistical micro mechanical model of anisotropic damage for SMC composites", *Composites science and technology*, Vol. 58, G.B., 1998, pp.759-763.
4. D. Gary Harlow and S. Leigh Phoenix, "The chain of bundles probability model for the strength of fibrous materials I: Analysis and conjectures", *Journal of composite materials*, Vol. 12, 1978, pp.195-214.
5. G'sell et JM Haudin, "Introduction à la mécanique des polymères", Institut National Polytechnique de Lorraine, 1995, pp. 345-393 ISBN: 2-905267-22-4.
6. JW Hitchon & DC Phillips, "The effect of specimen size on the strength of CFRP", *Composites*, Vol. 9, N°2, 1978, pp.119-124.
7. Koichi Goda & S. Leigh Phoenix, "reliability approach to the tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP composites by Monte-Carlo simulation in a shear-lag model", *Composites science and technology*, Vol. 50, 1994, pp.457-468.
8. F. Meraghni, C.J. Blakeman & M.L. Benzeggagh, "Effect of interfacial decohesion on stiffness reduction in a random discontinuous fibre composite containing matrix microcracks", *Composites science and technology*, Vol. 56, 1996, pp.541-555.
9. F.Meraghni & ML Benzeggagh, "Micromechanical modelling of matrix degradation in randomly oriented discontinuous fibre composites", *Composites Sciences and Technology*, Vol. 55, 1995, pp.171-186.
10. Mori T and Tanaka K, "Average stress in matrix and average elastic energy of materials with misfitting inclusion", *Acta. Metal.*, Vol. 21, 1973, pp. 571.
11. Mura T, "Micromechanics of defects in solids", Martinus Nijhoff, la Hague, 1982.
12. Mura T & Cheng P.C., "The elastic field outside an ellipsoidal inclusion", *ASME Journal of applied mechanics*, Vol. 44, 1977, pp.591-594.
13. Tsu – Wei Chou, "Microstructural design of fiber composites", Cambridge solid state science series, Cambridge university press (GB), ISBN: 0-521-35482-X, 1992, pp.99-168.
14. Tungyang Chen, George J.Dvorak, Yakov Benveniste, "Mori-Tanaka estimates of the overall elastic moduli of certain composite materials", *Journal of applied mechanics*, Vol. 59, 1992, pp.539-546.
15. MR Wisnom, "Relationship between strength variability and size effect in unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy", *Composites*, Vol. 22, N°1, 1991, pp.47-52.